

PRIN 2022 RESIST

DELIVERABLE 2000-C

31-05-2024

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA
ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
UNIVERSITÀ PERUGINA
UNIVERSITÀ POLITECNICA
DELLE MARCHE

Summary

1.	<i>INTRODUCTION</i>	3
2.	<i>CYBER-PHYSICAL SYSTEMS</i>	4
3.	<i>MEASURES FOR RESILIENCE AND CYBER RESILIENCE</i>	5
3.1.	<i>DEFINING RESILIENCE</i>	5
3.2.	<i>QUANTIFYING RESILIENCE</i>	7
3.3.	<i>FROM RESILIENCE TO CYBER RESILIENCE</i>	11
4.	<i>REVIEW ON CYBER-PHYSICAL ATTACKS</i>	12
4.1.	<i>IDENTIFICATION</i>	12
4.2.	<i>SCREENING</i>	13
4.3.	<i>ELIGIBILITY</i>	13
4.4.	<i>INCLUSION</i>	13
5.	<i>RESULTS</i>	22
5.1.	<i>CLASSIFICATION OF CYBER-PHYSICAL ATTACKS</i>	22
5.1.1.	<i>STEALTH ATTACK</i>	23
5.1.2.	<i>REPLAY ATTACK</i>	24
5.1.3.	<i>COVERT ATTACK</i>	25
5.1.4.	<i>DENIAL OF SERVICE ATTACK</i>	26
5.1.5.	<i>EAVESDROPPING ATTACK</i>	26
5.1.6.	<i>ZERO DYNAMICS ATTACK</i>	27
5.1.	<i>ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE WITH RESPECT TO THE CLASSIFICATION</i>	27
6.	<i>CONCLUSIONS</i>	28
	<i>ACKNOWLEDGEMENT</i>	31

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional risk management strategies focus on reducing either the probability of occurrence of adverse events or their impact, or both. This is usually done through mitigation in the form of prevention and protection. Even if such approaches are critical to prevent undesired events and their consequences, it has been acknowledged that not all events can be prevented (Aven, 2019). A growing consciousness on this problem resulted in a major emphasis on the theme of resilience, which can be seen as the ability to anticipate, respond and recover from unpredicted events (Dhs, 2014). The word “resilience” has increasingly been present in literature due to its role in reducing the risks associated with the inevitable disruption of systems. As such, studying resilience has become one of the most promising ways to accept the inevitability of failures, and to change it into an opportunity to continuously improve.

However, the affirmation of digitalization and connectivity in almost every field of technology brought additional challenges. Over the years, the concept of industrial automation has extended not only to actual production but also to its supporting systems, aiming at achieving a progressive integration of the production system with information systems. Industry 4.0 principles have entered almost every competitive industrial organization in the world (Sachdeva et al., 2018) as they improve operations and functionality, opening a whole new world of possibilities. As a consequence, the human component in control and information management operations has been reduced through the development of automation, especially when requiring continuous and repetitive actions. Nowadays, production establishments rely on systems, techniques, and technologies that execute sequential actions without the continuous intervention of humans, practically realizing the concept of a machine piloting another machine. Accordingly, cyber-physical systems (CPS) are increasingly present in factories and their application is transversal in all sectors. A CPS is characterized by a deep integration of elements with high computational, communication, and control capabilities (computers, PLCs, algorithms, data) along with physical elements (sensors, actuators) and processes (Rajkumar et al., 2010). A CPS is capable of continuously interacting with the physical system in which it operates through its capacity to compute, communicate and finally control the physical environment. Differently from pure IT systems, a CPS features a physical level where elements are monitored by sensors, and their outputs are appropriately processed to develop control strategies at an information level. The decisions made at this information level are then transmitted back to the physical level through actuators. This aspect brings additional vulnerabilities. While in the past, security measures focused on isolating critical system elements from the external world (making them physically inaccessible), it is now clear that the integration of sophisticated IT systems, the Internet of Things (IoT), the advanced automation and control techniques, the real-time data collection and analysis, and the communication networks have made these elements more exposed and vulnerable to cyber attacks. Malicious external actions can have significant consequences, not only in the IT realm (as for traditional information science) but also in the physical world, due to the nature of CPSs. The consequences of cyber attacks can potentially be disastrous for physical equipment, people, and the environment.

In this context, studying system safety and reliability is not possible by an evaluation of resilience as it is usually defined. It is necessary to consider not only failures strictly related to system physical components but also the anomalies related to the IT world. For this reason, a more specific concept, namely cyber resilience, started to be considered providing methodologies to assess and quantify resilience of industrial systems.

On these premises, this report aims to review academic literature on the theme of cyber-physical attacks in industrial establishments. The notion of CPS will be further detailed at first. Then, the concepts of resilience and cyber resilience will be examined, as they have been identified as a way to deal with cyber-physical attacks. These latter have been systematically reviewed with respect to the current available literature. To this extent, the report concludes drafting resilience metrics for the case study of the RESIST project.

2. CYBER-PHYSICAL SYSTEMS

There are different applications of CPS in industry and the network architecture varies based on the specific functional area. Regardless the inherent complexity, it is possible to highlight a generic CPS structure including a set of commonly adopted devices. **Figure 1** presents such a structure. Specifically, a cyber-physical system consists of three main layers in which information and signals move (Haque et al., 2019). Starting from the top (cf. **Figure 1**) the first encountered zone is the IT layer. The IT layer represents the business network in which decisions and business strategies are generated and information and data are stored. The IT layer is directly connected with a control layer usually represented by a Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition system (SCADA) which is a technology to monitor industrial plants and infrastructures based on CPSs. SCADA systems are typically composed of specific devices that are: (i) Master Terminal Unit (MTU) with Human Machine Interface (HMI); (ii) Remote Terminal Unit (RTU) or Programmable Logic Controller (PLC); (iii) sensors and actuators.

MTUs give access to the management of communications, collection of data, data storage and controls of sensor and actuators. Their interface is represented by HMIs. RTUs and PLCs are stand-alone data acquisition and control units that monitor and control industrial equipment. RTUs usually achieve more processing power than PLCs that are, on the other hand, usually more compact and general-purpose devices.

Sensors are monitoring elements responsible for measuring physical phenomena and feed controllers. Sensors can be seen as the inputs of the SCADA system: the data produced by sensors are sent to the upper layers via RTUs or PLCs. Actuators, instead, can be seen as outputs as long they translate the control signal generated by RTUs or PLCs into actions that correct the system functioning.

Finally, all system machines and tangible processes or infrastructures form the physical layer. Considering the connection between sensors and actuators and physical systems components, another sub-layer can be identified: the cyber-physical layer which obviously represents a characteristic feature of CPSs. The cyber-physical layer is the part of the control layer that directly interacts with the physical environment.

The risk of cyberattack can come into play when the IT and control layers communicate as long as the IT layer is open to the internet to interact with stakeholders or other business entities outside the industrial network. Adversaries also can take advantage of the heterogeneity of the different parts composing the CPS and their control and monitoring hardware and software systems (Humayed et al., 2017). The complexity of interconnection among components within the CPSs makes it difficult to identify and trace attacks, so, to improve system resilience, it becomes necessary to study system intrusion possibility, likewise their detection and prevention. An appropriate level of knowledge of vulnerabilities and attack vectors is needed, in this way, security and privacy policies can be updated, and the system can be designed to better respond and recover in case and adverse event happens.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a cyber-physical system structure. Adapted from (Haque et al., 2019).

3. MEASURES FOR RESILIENCE AND CYBER RESILIENCE

This section includes a collection of notions regarding resilience and cyber resilience. The aim is to highlight common aspects reaching a definition of resilience and cyber resilience. With respect to the final outcome of the report, methods presented in scientific literature to measure resilience are included, too.

3.1. Defining resilience

The concept of resilience was formally introduced referring to ecology problems as the persistence of relationships within a system, and it has been initially measured by the system's ability to absorb change-state variable, driving variables, and parameters yet still persist (Holling, 2013). Since then, the concept of resilience has been declined in several different manners adapting it to different science domains. For example, the work by (Hosseini et al., 2016) individuates four major disciplinary perspectives in which resilience problems have been consistently approached. The identified resilience application domains are societal, organizational, economic, and engineering.

The concept of resilience has been well studied in subdomains of the societal domain such as ecology, psychology, and sociology, as it was from these branches of knowledge that it was firstly theorized. In social domains resilience is always seen as an inner capacity of individuals, communities, and environments. For example, in the Community and Regional Resilience Institute report (Rose, 2009), it has been defined as the capability to predict risks, restrict adverse consequences and return rapidly through survival, adaptability and growth in the face of turbulent changes.

Concerning the organizational domain, the theme of resilience has emerged from the need of enterprises to respond to a rapidly changing business environment. The work by (Sheffi, 2006) defines organizational resilience as the ability to keep or recover a steady state after a disruptive event or in the presence of continuous stress, and, the resilience of companies, as the ability and speed companies have in returning at their normal performance level following a disruptive event.

A very specific definition of economic resilience has been provided, too (Martin, 2012): here resilience is defined as the capacity to reconfigure and adapt, its structure (firms, industries, technologies, institutions) so as to maintain an acceptable growth path in output, employment, and wealth over time.

Lastly, concerning the engineering domain, a large research trend is the one connected to Resilience Engineering (Hollnagel et al., 2012), which stresses how understanding of the normal functioning of a socio-technical system is as important as understanding how it fails. Another interesting point of view has been given from The American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) that defined resilience as the ability of a system to sustain external and internal disruptions without discontinuity of performing system's functionality or, if the functionality is disconnected, to fully recover rapidly. Since infrastructure systems (i.e. water distribution networks, energy production plants, transportation systems, etc.) are subdomains of the engineering domain, as long their construction and restoration require engineering knowledge, a newsworthy definition is the one given by the National Infrastructure Advisory Council (NIAC). NIAC defined resilience of infrastructures as the ability to predict, absorb, adapt, and quickly recover from a disruptive event as a natural disaster could be.

There is not a single view about how to define resilience. The above list includes just some of the resilience characterizations that could be found in literature, yet many others exist. The difficulty of finding a general definition of resilience is surely justified by the potential of this theme that can be used and declined in almost every aspect of knowledge. However, some common aspects can be identified in all the studies on resilience, and listing them can help defining it:

- Many researchers focused on the capability of a system to absorb and adapt to disruptive events; so, it can be stated that vulnerability first, and recovery then are necessary items to characterize resilient performance;
- Some studies empathize that is important to return to a steady state performance level, while others do not impose a perfect return to pre-disruption state. However, the state reached after recovery represent another important aspect in evaluating resilience;
- For engineering and technical systems, reliability is often considered to be an important feature to measure the ability to prevent a disruption;
- Some definitions defined design for resilience in terms of preparedness activities (i.e. before disruption occurrence), others also point at the role of recovery activities (i.e. post disruption occurrence) to achieve resilience.

All these definitions and reasonings find a practical application in resilience evaluation procedures that can be divided into two types: qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative approach includes methods to assess resilience without numerical descriptions and contains two main applications: (i) conceptual frameworks that offers best practices, (ii) semi-quantitative indices that permit assessment of qualitative aspects of resilience. On the other hand, a quantitative approach aims to calculate specific metrics to give a measure of resilience. This report focuses on quantitative approaches since it is meant to draft resilience metrics for the plant serving as case study for the RESIST project.

3.2. Quantifying resilience

To evaluate resilience from a quantitative point of view, it is fundamental to identify proper metrics which can be seen as a measure of systems' characteristic performance. It is clear from **Section 3.1** that resilience is somehow connected to the response of a system, and so to its functioning, in case a disruptive event occurs. A time dependent function that describes system operations or overall performance, or a specific part of them, is defined as resilience metrics. **Figure 2** shows an example of a metric $M(t)$ plotted over time; the metric is built as a percentage of actual system performance compared to a perfect one. When the plot starts, the system is working at its optimal condition with a performance $M(t)$ equal to 100. At time t_0 something happens, and the system gets perturbed; this reflects on the performance metric $M(t)$ through a loss of 70 points, so $M(t_0)$ is equal to 30. From that moment the system starts to linearly recover from the shock and increases its performance. At time t_1 the initial performance value is reached again $M(t_1)$ equals 100 again and normal working conditions are completely restored.

Figure 2. System performance over time, with resilience triangle highlighted.

Starting from a graphical definition as for **Figure 2**, (Tierney & Bruneau, 2007) suggested a method to measure resilience through the evaluation of the dimension of the resilience triangle. With respect to **Figure 2** it is possible to compute the resilience triangle (ABD) area A_r as follows:

$$A_r = \frac{\overline{AD} \cdot \overline{AB}}{2} \quad (1)$$

Or more in general:

$$A_r = [100 \cdot (t_1 - t_0)] - \int_{t_0}^{t_1} M(t) \quad (2)$$

Where the first term represents the area under the performance curve in the time range from t_0 to t_1 if no perturbation would have taken place.

The value of A_r gives a measure of system resilience: smaller triangles identify more resilient systems; bigger ones are built if systems take more time to restore initial performance or produce a major performance loss. This measure was based on the observation that a resilient system reduces the probability of failures and enhances recovery. For this reason, resilience is measured by the functionality of the system after an external shock occurs including the time it takes to return to the initial level of performance. (Attoh-Okine et al., 2009) proposed different paths to describe the loss of performance and system recovery. For example, **Figure 2** shows a sudden failure of the system in t_0 . Using the concept of resilience as illustrated in **Figure 2**, they suggested its evaluation through a resilience index defined as follow:

$$R = \frac{\int_{t_0}^{t_1} M(t) dt}{100 \cdot (t_1 - t_0)} \quad (3)$$

That is equal to 1 if the two areas have the same extension, describing a perfect response and maximum resilience. Note that also the resilience index from (Attoh-Okine et al., 2009) is correlated to the dimension of the ABD triangle.

Starting from **Equation 3** a resilience framework called “the four Rs” was proposed. It is based on the definition of four parameter, namely:

- Robustness (R1): strength or ability of the system and system elements to withstand a given level of stress without suffering degradation or loss of functionality;
- Redundancy (R2): extent to which system and system elements exist and are capable of satisfying functional requirements in the event of disruption, degradation, or loss of functionality. It translates in the identification of substitutes that satisfy functional requirements in case of performance degradation;
- Resourcefulness (R3): capacity to identify problems, establish priorities and mobilize resources when a condition that threatens to disrupt system and system elements exists. It can be further conceptualized as the ability to apply material and resources in the process of recovery;
- Rapidity (R4): capacity to meet priorities and achieve goals in a timely way in order to contain losses, recover functionality and avoid future disruptions.

Starting from there, (Bruneau & Reinhorn, 2007) suggested a four-dimensional description of resilience through the four Rs which permits to evaluate resilience from a quantitative point of view. **Figure 2** shows a metric on the vertical and horizontal axes, a plot of this type permits to notice the magnitude of robustness (R1) and rapidity (R4) defined as follow:

$$R1 = \overline{BC} \quad (4)$$

$$R4 = \frac{\overline{AB}}{t_0 - t_1} \quad (5)$$

However, **Figure 2** can be expanded in a three-dimensional and four-dimensional plot to capture the means of resilience in terms of resourcefulness and redundancy. In **Figure 3** a third axis permits to evaluate different resilient responses adding resources. Different resources can be used to reduce time to recover, represented by the red segments in the plot, beyond what is expected by the base “normal” condition illustrated in **Figure 2**.

Figure 3. Three-dimensional plot of system performance over time, adding the resources dimension to the measurement of resilience.

The fourth dimension of resilience is visible by grouping multiple three-dimensional plots as the type shown in **Figure 3**. The concept of redundancy can be evaluated through a connected response of multiple systems or systems elements. For example, while **Figure 3** could represent the resilient response of a single hospital in case of a seismic event, **Figure 4** could represent the resiliency of all care facilities in the same geographical area. In the case of seismic event is clear that resilience of the health care system can be evaluated also by taking into account resourcefulness as linkages between every part of it.

Figure 4. Four-dimensional plot of system performance, adding the resourcefulness dimension to the measurement of resilience.

Based on the works mentioned above, some research (Aven, 2019) suggests a more general quantitative resilience approach. Resilience is considered as persistence of system's performance under uncertain disturbances or disruption events. The framework is an extension of the bi-dimensional resilience concept on performance – time axes. Specifically, the system performance metric $M(t)$ is plotted on the graph also considering an aging effect that implies a system's degradation over time. An incident is inserted at time t_i with a probabilistic occurrence rate λ according to a Poisson process. Time t_i represents the failure event that has a duration of ΔT_f so, it concludes at time t_f . The failure is followed by a recovery event with a duration ΔT_r so, the recovery concludes at time t_r . The disruption event has a total duration equal to:

$$\Delta T_d = \Delta T_f + \Delta T_r \quad (6)$$

As it possible to notice in **Figure 5**, different types of failures and recovery events are illustrated: (i) brittle, (ii) ductile and (iii) graceful concerning failures in red; (i) better than new, (ii) as good as new, (iii) better than old, (iv) as good as old, (v) worse than old concerning recovery phase in blue. The figure also shows the aging performance trajectory and estimated aging trajectory after recovery. The proposed measure of resilience (R) is:

$$R = \frac{t_i + F\Delta T_f + R\Delta T_r}{t_i + \Delta T_f + \Delta T_r} \quad (7)$$

Where failure profile Fa is defined as:

$$Fa = \frac{\int_{t_i}^{t_f} f dt}{\int_{t_i}^{t_f} Q dt} \quad (8)$$

And recovery profile Re is defined as:

$$Re = \frac{\int_{t_f}^{t_r} r dt}{\int_{t_f}^{t_r} Q dt} \quad (9)$$

The failure profile value gives a measure of robustness and redundancy; on the other hand, the recovery profile value can be considered a measure of resourcefulness and rapidity. This framework represents a very generic approach to resilience measurement and gives the possibility to cast it to multiples case study.

3.3. From resilience to cyber resilience

The characteristics of system resilience should be slightly updated when dealing with CPSs. Indeed, the increasing amount of software and communication networks in CPSs has made them more vulnerable to cyber-attacks. However, the main focus in CPSs design had lied on functionality of system elements and non-functional aspects such as reliability, efficiency, safety, and usability, not usually considering in depth the cybersecurity aspect. Most of the prior development effort has been focused on dealing with system complexity to guarantee system operation under severe operational environments (Rashid et al., 2017). However, in recent years, the cybersecurity aspect has been considered more and more important in design phase since the occurrence of failure events related to cyber-security issues in CPSs has become a proven risk (Yaacoub et al., 2020). Even if these systems comply with the general cybersecurity requirements for IT systems, the close interaction with the physical environment opens new opportunity for attackers and potentially more severe impact. An increasing amount of research on this topic has moved the focus on resilience of CPSs through the so-called cyber resilience or capacity of a system to absorb and recover or adapt to adverse events caused by cyber-attacks. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) provided a framework to improve cybersecurity and resilience of critical infrastructures based on the identification of five functions (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2018):

- Identify. Develop understanding of risks systems, assets data and capabilities are subjected;
- Protect. Develop and implement appropriate safeguards to ensure service;
- Detect. Identify the occurrence of a cyber-attack event;
- Respond. Take action regarding a cyber-attack detected event;
- Recover. Maintain plans for resilience and restore any capabilities or services that were impaired due to the cyber-security event.

Detailed guidelines to ensure Industrial Control System (ICS) security are suggested by NIST, too, as long control systems represent the cyber-attack vulnerable part of CPSs. (Wei & Ji, 2010) identified a resilient industrial system as a system that satisfies the following characteristics:

- Ability to minimize undesirable consequences of an incident;
- Ability to mitigate most of the undesirable incidents;
- Ability to restore normal operation within a short time.

Moreover, (Haque et al., 2018) provides a methodology to quantify cyber-resilience metrics with a quantitative approach adapting the 4Rs framework illustrated before (section 2.1). Resilience fundamentals and definitions provided in **Section 3.1** are obviously still valid even if talking about cyber related issues; the works referenced in the previous lines offer major contributions on resilience problems seen from a more specific point of view but do not drastically change resilience evaluation techniques and reasonings. For this reason, the better way to clarify the purpose of a cyber-resilience study lays in an appropriate knowledge of a CPS functioning and on the consciousness of multiple cyber-attacks scenarios that could verify. These latter are systematically reviewed and discussed in **Section 4**.

4. REVIEW ON CYBER-PHYSICAL ATTACKS

This report aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current scientific literature pertaining to cyber-attacks. The purpose of such a review is twofold. Firstly, it serves as a baseline to classify cyber-physical attacks from a bottom-up perspective. Then it is meant to highlight trends and criticalities of cyber-physical attacks -related studies as for the current state of the art, eventually demonstrating guiding the design of simulations in the RESIST project. To carry out this work, the PRISMA methodology was used. The PRISMA provides guidelines for reviews, as per the following core steps:

1. Definition and aims of the review: to develop a review it is necessary to define some features to identify the research question and the criteria of selection to analyze the documentation. For this reason, the following features allow to define the aims of scope:
 - Research question to ensure a specific, measurable, and relevant content for the analysis.
 - Criteria of selection outlining the review process. Include criteria for study inclusion/exclusion, search strategies, data extraction, and statistical analysis plan.
 - Academic databases search engine to conduct a comprehensive literature search using academic databases to identify and extract the data document in terms of inclusion and exclusion criteria.
2. Study and data selection: to allow the screening of the documents to be analyzed. Then, from the documents, relevant data will be extracted from selected studies using a standardized form.
3. Eligibility documentation: to evaluate the representativeness of each included study.
4. Analysis of the documentation: to synthesize the elected documents, employing either narrative synthesis or bibliometric synthesis.

The PRISMA framework has been selected as it ensures transparency and completeness in reporting reviews, enhancing the reliability and usability of the research. Moreover, opting for a scoping review has been deemed appropriate to assess the extent of a topic's coverage in the literature and provide dependable insights into the quantity, nature, and other attributes of relevant publications.

4.1. Identification

The first step consists in identifying the database and defining the search query. Specifically, the activity of collecting and selecting papers was conducted through the SCOPUS search engine. The query used is the following:

“TITLE-ABS-KEY (“cyber” AND “physical” AND “attack”) AND (“manufacturing” OR “industrial” AND “plant”))”

The output papers were 578. Then, focusing only on papers written in English and linked to “Engineering” as a subject area, allowed to discard 199 papers, resulting in 379 remaining documents to be further analyzed.

4.2. Screening

This step consists of reviewing titles and abstracts to determine papers’ relevance with respect to the objective of the review. Accordingly, 279 articles were identified as out of scope from the title and abstract reading. Specifically, these articles were those not presenting industrial plants as a case study, or in which the aim of the paper was not cyber-attack in the CPS. Therefore, the papers excluded from the research based their analysis on the following types of industries: mining, private services such as commerce, financial services, and telecommunications services; infrastructures (e.g., constructions and smart cities); public services (e.g., healthcare and public services); maritime and transport (railway, road transport, and civil aviation). In addition, other types of applications have been excluded from the analysis, including cyber-forensic analysis and leaking information attacks.

4.3. Eligibility

The third step consists of assessing full texts of potentially relevant studies. This step allowed a second screening of the articles that were not in line with the objectives of the research. In this regard, 61 more were considered out of scope after the full-text reading. Among them, the following articles were identified as outliers: (i) 3 documents exhibited discrepancies between the title, abstract, keywords and the full text; (ii) 6 documents presented a literature review of a pool of cyber-attacks in the industrial process; and (iii) 2 papers focused on the classification of the cyber-physical risk in the industrial plants. Furthermore, an additional 50 documents have been excluded from the analysis due to their content being outside the scope of the application. Among these 50 papers, 28 documents were related to the design of frameworks for: (i) the identification of a cyber-attack in CPS; or (ii) the mitigation of the risk due to cyber-attacks. Both approaches have been excluded since the documents did not provide an explanation of the types of cyber-attack, nor discussed the consequences or impact of such attacks on the CPS. The remaining 22 documents have been excluded since the presented analysis were not related to the physical impacts but focused only on the cyber aspects of CPSs. At the end of the eligibility step, 39 papers were included in the literature review.

4.4. Inclusion

The last step of the PRISMA methodology involves detailed full-text analysis of previously selected documents. This detailed reading allowed the authors to deeply analyze the remaining 39 papers and create **Table 1**, which will be leveraged later in **Section 5** for complete discussion. Specifically, **Table 5** includes: (i) the reference to the paper being reviewed, (ii) the title and a short summary of the paper’s content, (iii) the industrial sector on which the study is focused (among the ones considered relevant), (iv) the type of system being analyzed, (v) the type of cyber-physical attack being analyzed.

Table 1 Papers on the theme of cyber-physical attacks within the scope of this literature review.

Reference	Title and summary	Industrial sector	Type of cyber-physical system	Type of cyber-physical attack
(S. Yuan et al., 2024)	<p><u>Integrated process safety and process security risk assessment of industrial cyber-physical systems in chemical plants</u></p> <p>This study develops a systematic approach to construct accident scenarios concerning both safety hazards and security threats and performs a probabilistic risk assessment of chemical facilities considering the interdependency between safety-associated events and security-associated events.</p>	Chemical Industries	Chemical reaction in agitated reactor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - False data injection - Denial of Service - Setpoint manipulation
(Iaiani et al., 2023)	<p><u>Identification of cyber-risks for the control and safety instrumented systems: a synergic framework for the process industry</u></p> <p>In the present study, a synergic framework of tools is described and applied to a case study (offshore oil and gas platform for gas compression), supporting the systematic identification of the risks that can originate as a result of a malicious interference to the BPCS and SIS. The authors presented a novel AI-based framework to address this issue and examine its capabilities for the example of Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF), demonstrating real-time recovery from attack-induced inter-road voids with unprecedented sub-road spatial resolution.</p>	Oil and gas	Gas compression on offshore platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eavesdropping - False data injection
(Mangroli a et al., 2024)	<p><u>Continuing minimal-defect production under material integrity cyberattacks</u></p> <p>The authors presented a novel AI-based framework to address this issue and examine its capabilities for the example of Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF), demonstrating real-time recovery from attack-induced inter-road voids with unprecedented sub-road spatial resolution.</p>	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Fused Filament Fabrication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - False data injection - Setpoint manipulation - Time delay

(Pearce et al., 2021)	<p><u>FLAW3D: A Trojan-Based Cyber Attack on the Physical Outcomes of Additive Manufacturing</u></p> <p>In this work, the authors demonstrate this risk by presenting the design and study of a malicious Trojan (the FLAW3D bootloader) for AVR-based Marlin-compatible 3-D printers (>100 commercial models).</p>	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	3D printing	- Code injection - Data tampering
(Khalid et al., 2022)	<p><u>Understanding vulnerabilities in cyber physical production systems</u></p> <p>In this paper, the authors developed a risk assessment based on system vulnerability of a CPPS developed for a use case requirement and performed a simulated approach by launching a cyber-attack and measuring the causal effect to identify implications on human worker safety.</p>	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Industrial robot Pick&Place	- Setpoint manipulation
(Graves et al., 2021)	<p><u>Sabotaging metal additive manufacturing: Powder delivery system manipulation and material-dependent effects</u></p> <p>In this paper, the authors focus on attacks aiming to sabotage metal parts produced using Powder Bed Fusion (PBF), a metal AM process used to manufacture near net shaped parts for safety critical systems. Specifically, they focus on the Powder Delivery System (PDS), an integral PBF subsystem.</p>	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Powder bed fusion - making metal parts in powder bed fusion (AM - additive manufacturing)	- Code injection - Data tampering - Setpoint manipulation
(Chekole et al., 2021)s	<p><u>SCOPE: Secure Compiling of PLCs in Cyber-Physical Systems</u></p> <p>In this work, the authors propose to enforce a full-stack memory-safety (covering user-space and kernel-space attack surfaces) based on secure compiling of PLCs to detect memory-safety attacks in CPS. Furthermore, to ensure availability, we enforce a resilient mitigation technique that bypasses illegal memory access instructions at runtime by dynamically instrumenting low-level code.</p>	Utilities (water)	Water purification process	- Code injection - Setpoint manipulation
(Maggi et al., 2021)	<p><u>Smart Factory Security: A Case Study on a Modular Smart Manufacturing System</u></p> <p>In this paper a practical case study showing attack scenarios that have</p>	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Modular manufacturing system - 7-station integrated	- Data tampering - Code injection - Covert channel

	been validated on a real modular smart manufacturing system, and suggest practical security counter measures has been described.		manufacturing system for smartphone production	
(Ranabhat et al., 2018)	<u>Optimal sabotage attack on composite material parts</u> In this article the authors develop a simulation approach to designing sabotage attacks against composite material parts.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Reinforced composite materials-combination of two or more materials with different properties	- Data tampering
(Zhang et al., 2019)	<u>Towards automated safety vetting of PLC code in real-world plants</u> In this paper the authors propose VetPLC, a temporal context-aware, program analysis-based approach to produce timed event sequences that can be used for automatic safety vetting.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Car model assembly line	- Code injection - Data tampering - Setpoint manipulation
(Hindy et al., 2019)	<u>Improving SIEM for critical SCADA water infrastructures using machine learning</u> In this paper, the authors present a model that detects anomaly events in a water system controlled by SCADA. Six Machine Learning techniques have been used in building and evaluating the model.	Utilities (water)	Water distribution infrastructure model	- Denial of Service - Spoofing
(Wu et al., 2018)	<u>Establishment of intrusion detection testbed for Cyber Manufacturing systems</u> In this work a Cyber Manufacturing System (CMS) testbed was built for the purpose of: (i) simulating cyber-physical intrusions in CMS environment, (ii) collecting data for a cyber-physical intrusion detection system - DACDI (Define, Audit, Correlate, Disclose, and Improve), and (iii) building an environment with necessary set of equipment for further CMS security investigations.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	CMS (cyber manufacturing system) model. AM/SM (additive/subtractive) physical environment.	- Data tampering - Code injection - Eavesdropping
(Kang et al., 2015)	<u>Investigating cyber-physical attacks against IEC 61850 photovoltaic inverter installations</u> This paper addresses a deep investigation of attacks against the manufacturing message specification of IEC 61850, which is expected to become one of the most widely used	Utilities (electricity)	Photovoltaic installation	- Eavesdropping - Setpoint manipulation - False data injection

	communication services in Smart Grids.			
(Dehlaghi-Ghadim et al., 2023)	<u>ICSSIM — A framework for building industrial control systems security testbeds</u> In this paper, the authors present ICSSIM, a framework for building customized virtual ICS security testbeds in which various cyber threats and network attacks can be effectively and efficiently investigated.	Utilities (water)	Water bottling line	- Denial of Service - Replay - False data injection - Man in the middle - Eavesdropping - Setpoint manipulation
(Nedeljko vić, Jakovljević, Miljković, et al., 2020)	<u>Detection of Cyber-attacks in Systems with Distributed Control based on Support Vector Regression</u> In this paper the authors present a method for detection of attacks on sensor signals, based on ϵ insensitive support vector regression (ϵ -SVR).	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Electro-pneumatic positioning system	- False data injection
(Ibrahim et al., 2019)	<u>Attack graph implementation and visualization for cyber physical systems</u> In this paper, three cyber physical systems case studies of a pressurized water nuclear power plant (NPP), an industrial control system (ICS), and a vehicular network system (VNS) are examined, formally presented, and implemented utilizing Architecture Analysis and Design Language, determining system design, links, weaknesses, resources, potential attack instances, and their pre-and post-conditions.	Energy	Thermonuclear plant	- Eavesdropping - Code injection - Denial of Service
(Huang et al., 2018)	<u>Assessing the physical impact of cyberattacks on industrial cyber-physical systems</u> A new risk assessment method is presented in this paper to quantify the impact of cyberattacks on the physical system of ICPSs.	Energy	Steam generator	- Eavesdropping - Man in the middle - False data injection - Code injection - Denial of Service
(Takiddin et al., 2022)	<u>Data-Driven Detection of Stealth Cyber-Attacks in DC Microgrids</u> This article answers two important research questions: 1) Which data-driven detection scheme offers the best detection performance against stealth cyber-attacks in dc microgrids? 2) What is the detection performance improvement when	Utilities (electricity)	Microgrid of distributed DC (direct current) cooperative generators with DC-DC buck converters	- False data injection - Denial of Service

	fusing two features (i.e., current and voltage data) for training compared with using a single feature (i.e., current)?			
(Katulić et al., 2023)	<u>Protecting Modbus/TCP-Based Industrial Automation and Control Systems Using Message Authentication Codes</u> This paper presents a novel method for enhancing the cybersecurity of Modbus/TCP-based IACSs by implementing an authentication method based on message authentication codes (MACs).	Utilities (water)	Plant for treatment and potable water	- Eavesdropping - Denial of Service - Spoofing - Man in the middle - Setpoint manipulation
(Loukas et al., 2017)	<u>Computation offloading of a vehicle's continuous intrusion detection workload for energy efficiency and performance</u> Computation offloading is widely used and studied for mobile devices due to their limited processing power and battery dependence, making it beneficial to offload demanding tasks to remote servers or cloud infrastructures. Typically, the offloaded tasks on mobile devices are not time-critical and are performed infrequently. However, the concept is also practical for continuous tasks on more powerful cyber-physical systems where timeliness is crucial. A case study illustrating this is real-time intrusion detection on a robotic vehicle.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Remotely controlled robotic vehicle	- False data injection - Covert channel - Data tampering
(Robles-Durazno et al., 2021)	<u>Implementation and evaluation of physical, hybrid, and virtual testbeds for cybersecurity analysis of industrial control systems</u> This manuscript describes, implements, and evaluates physical, hybrid, and virtual application of a clean water supply system developed for cybersecurity research.	Utilities (water)	Drinking water distribution system	- Code injection - Setpoint manipulation - Data tampering
(Burbano et al., 2021)	<u>Dynamic data integration for resilience to sensor attacks in multi-agent systems</u> This paper presents a practical implementation of a strategy to detect cyber-attacks and mitigate their effects on sensors of a multi-agent system.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Training of leader-follower type robots	- Denial of Service - False data injection

(Mahvash et al., 2024)	<p><u>A New Nonlinear Virtual Inertia Approach to Mitigate Destructive Effects of Cyber Attacks on Active Power and Rotor Speed Profiles of Wind Turbine DFIG Sustainable Energy Production</u></p> <p>In this paper, a novel nonlinear virtual inertia control (VIC) is suggested to effectively mitigate the destructive effects of the important cyber-attacks including false data injection attack (FDIA), denial of service (DoS) and hijack attack (HjA), happening with the active power and rotor speed profiles of DFIGs in an AC microgrid (ACMG).</p>	Utilities (electricity)	Grid of DFIG wind generators (doubly fed induction generators - stator and rotor windings excited externally to the machine)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - False data injection - Denial of Service - Data tampering - Setpoint manipulation
(Palleti, Mishra, et al., 2021)	<p><u>Can replay attacks designed to steal water from water distribution systems remain undetected?</u></p> <p>In this paper an experimental study was conducted with replay attacks launched on an operational water distribution (WADI) plant to understand under what conditions an attacker/attack can remain undetected while stealing water.</p>	Utilities (water)	Drinking water plant and distribution network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Replay - Spoofing
(Elnour et al., 2023)	<p><u>A Machine Learning Based Framework for Real-Time Detection and Mitigation of Sensor False Data Injection Cyber-Physical Attacks in Industrial Control Systems</u></p> <p>This work presents a distributed, machine learning based attack detection and mitigation framework for sensor false data injection cyber-physical attacks in industrial control systems. It is developed using the system's standard operational data and validated using a hybrid testbed of a reverse osmosis plant. A MATLAB/Simulink-based simulation model of the process validated with actual data from a local plant is used.</p>	Utilities (water)	Two-stage reverse osmosis water purification plant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - False data injection
(Banik et al., 2023)	<p><u>Implementing Man-in-the-Middle Attack to Investigate Network Vulnerabilities in Smart Grid Test-bed</u></p> <p>In order to strengthen resistance to cyber-attacks, this study introduces a</p>	Utilities (electricity)	Intelligent type electric grid (generation, transmission and distribution)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Man in the middle - Eavesdropping - Code injection

	test bed for cyber-physical systems that operate in real-time.			
(Stetter et al., 2022)	<u>Cyber-Security Aware Design of Automated Systems</u> This paper proposes a systemic approach to design processes and products for increased cyber security. This approach is based on an attack model and is explained based on an automated storage system.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Automated warehouse with AGV (automated guided vehicle) transport system	- False data injection - Eavesdropping
(Coppolino et al., 2022)	<u>A framework for Seveso-compliant cyber-physical security testing in sensitive industrial plants</u> A Seveso-compliant Seveso cyber-physical security testing in sensitive industrial plants is examined.	Chemical Industries	Chemical storage and transfer terminal	- Eavesdropping - Code injection - Data tampering
(Dedousis et al., 2021)	<u>A security-aware framework for designing industrial engineering processes</u> In this paper, the authors present a framework that extends previous, preliminary work on the integration of security in industrial engineering design practices, and provide an algorithmic approach that effectively reduces risk during industrial system design lifecycles.	Oil and gas	Refinery for production of liquefied petroleum gas	- Replay - Spoofing - Denial of Service - Eavesdropping
(Dong et al., 2022)	<u>State Estimation and Attack Reconstruction of Picking Robot for a Cyber-Physical System</u> In this work a novel method based on the unknown input observer is proposed to reconstruct sensor attacks and estimate system states for fruit and vegetable picking robot cyber-physical systems.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Picking Robot	- False data injection - Denial of Service - Replay
(Olijnyk et al., 2022)	<u>Design and Emulation of Physics-Centric Cyberattacks on an Electrical Power Transformer</u> The subject of this research is how physics-centric modules of malware can cause physical damage to power grid equipment. This research simulates a power transformer and a set of its protection algorithms.	Utilities (electricity)	Transformer on electrical grid in substation	- Eavesdropping - Code injection - Replay
(Van Bossuyt & O'Halloran, 2019)	<u>A Method to Choose between Automation and Human Operators for Recovery Actions during a Cyber Attack</u> This paper presents a method of determining if a human operator or an	Energy	Fuel pool cooling subsystem (nuclear power plant)	- Denial of Service - False data injection

	automated system is more appropriate to complete a recovery action during a cyber-attack. The method is useful during the conceptual phase of system design where architecture changes have minimal impact on the cost and schedule of the system design effort.			
(Arnaboldi et al., 2020)	<u>Modelling Load-Changing Attacks in Cyber-Physical Systems</u> The paper focuses on a particular and distressing attack where coordinated malware infected IoT units are maliciously employed to synchronously turn on or off high-wattage appliances, affecting the grid's primary control management.	Energy	Intelligent type electric grid (generation, transmission and distribution)	- Eavesdropping - False data Injection
(Umsonst & Sandberg, 2022)	<u>Experimental evaluation of sensor attacks and defense mechanisms in feedback systems</u> In this work, the authors evaluate theoretical results, developed under linearity assumptions, on the feasibility of, the worst-case impact of, and defense mechanisms against a stealthy sensor attack in an experimental setup. The goal is to determine if this sensor attack poses a threat to real systems as well.	Chemical Industries	Temperature control system for chemical reaction	- False data injection - Eavesdropping
(Dai et al., 2024)	<u>Fuzzy high order differentiator observer based resilient control for distributed battery energy storage systems against unbounded FDI attacks</u> This paper addresses the issue of frequency recovery in distributed battery energy storage systems (BESSs) and the balancing of the state of charge (SOC) after secondary control inputs have been subjected to false data injection attacks (FDI).	Utilities (electricity)	Distributed energy storage system	- False data injection
(Nedeljko vić, Jakovljević, & Miljković, 2020)	<u>The detection of sensor signal attacks in industrial control systems</u> In this paper, a method for sensor signal attacks detection in a continuous time controlled systems has been proposed..	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Continuous time controlled systems (power plant)	- Sensor signal attack
(Yampolskiy et al., 2015)	<u>Security challenges of additive manufacturing with metals and alloys</u> This work focuses on attacks that seek to change the physical properties of additive-manufactured components.	Manufacturing : Mechanical and electrical engineering	Additive manufacturing with 3D printer	- Code injection

(Palleti, Adepu, et al., 2021)	<p><u>Cascading effects of cyber-attacks on interconnected critical infrastructure</u></p> <p>In this paper, the authors report a study to investigate the cascading effects of cyber-attacks on two interdependent critical infrastructure namely, a Secure water treatment plant (SWaT) and a Water Distribution System (WADI).</p>	Utilities (water)	The industrial process is compounded by Secure Water Treatment (SWaT) and Water Distribution (WADI)	- Replay - False data injection
(Carreño et al., 2020)	<p><u>An adversarial model for attack vector vulnerability analysis on power and gas delivery operations</u></p> <p>In this paper the authors present a model that can be used to quantify the impact of cyber-attacks on electricity and gas delivery operations. We model activation of cyber-attack vectors that attempt to gain access to pipeline gas compressor controls using a continuous-time Markov chain over a state space based on the gas operator Industrial Control System firewall zone partition.</p>	Energy	Supply fuel for gas generation	- Cyber-attack vector

5. RESULTS

5.1. Classification of cyber-physical attacks

To leverage the results of the review, a classification was made with respect to the attack being discussed in the paper (i.e., Type of cyber-physical attack, cf. **Table 1**). The classification of cyber-physical attacks was inspired by one already available in literature (Teixeira et al., 2012), which relies on the construction of a cyber-physical attack three-dimensional space as shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5. Space for classification of cyber-physical attacks. Adapted from (Teixeira et al., 2012).

The three suggested dimensions of a cyber-physical attack are:

- *System knowledge*: a priori system knowledge can be used by the attacker to generate more complex attacks; this means they will be harder to detect and with more severe consequences. Some specific and noted cyber-attacks need system knowledge to become effective as shown in **Figure 5**;
- *Disclosure resources*: it represents a dimension of how much sensitive information the attacker is able to obtain and exploit during the attack. Notice that disclosure resources alone cannot be used to disrupt system operations, an example is the eavesdropping type of attack in **Figure 6**;
- *Disruption resources*: it is the capability of the attack to affect system operations. This happens for example when data integrity is violated, and system operations changes consequently.

According to these dimensions, all the types of cyber-physical attacks in **Table 1** are included in 6 strategies, as detailed in **Table 2**, and positioned in the classification space for readers convenience in **Figure 5**. Additionally, details about these strategies are presented in the following paragraphs.

Table 2. Aggregation of types of cyber-physical attacks (as from the literature review) within strategies in **Figure 5**.

<i>Cyber-physical attack strategy</i>	<i>Denomination of cyber-physical attack (as from the literature review)</i>
Stealth attack	False data injection
	Data tampering
	Spoofing
Covert attack	Man in the middle
	Covert channel
	Code injection
	Setpoint manipulation
Denial of service attack	Time delay
	Denial of service
Replay attack	Replay
	Spoofing
Eavesdropping attack	Eavesdropping
Zero dynamics attack	Setpoint manipulation
	Cyber-attack vector

5.1.1. Stealth attack

Stealth attack (Cárdenas et al., n.d.; Dan & Sandberg, 2010) or false-data injection attack (Liu et al., 2011) represent a strategy of cyber-physical attacks that modify some sensors readings through an interference to disrupt the behavior of the system. They use false-data injection in order to generate a wrong control decision able to cause a malfunction. The inserted data does not alter the sensor measurement variations forcing the controller to slowly drive the system to wrong functioning. These types of attacks are basically undetectable if a check is only made by a detector that verifies the sensor measurements and their compatibility with the system dynamic. Obviously, in order to perform a

stealth attack the adversary needs to have an appropriate knowledge of the system: its dynamic, command signals and control detection thresholds. Popular false-data injection techniques are:

- Surge attack: the goal is to maximize the damage in the shorter time. No particular injection strategy is followed, knowing the system dynamic and the detectors threshold an undetectable data that leads to a rapid system breakdown is inserted (i.e. substitute the real data) on the communication channel between sensors and control layer;
- Bias-injection attack: through a physical interference the attacker modifies sensors readings injecting a constant bias signal (i.e. the sensor output signal is summed with another signal). This leads to wrong control decisions and cause malfunctions in a slower but more undetectable way since the measurement changes more gently;
- Geometric-injection attack: it is a particular type of intelligent bias-injection in which the bias-injection is gradual. This results even more difficult to notice and potentially more harmful.

A scheme that shows how stealth attacks operate in a CPS is provided in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. Scheme for stealth attack strategy.

5.1.2. Replay attack

Replay attack is a particular type of spoofing cyber-attack with potential physical effects structured in two phases that the adversary manages to conduct at the same time. At first, (i) the attacker modifies sensors readings by replicating previous measurements that correspond to a normal operation condition; then, (ii) control inputs are modified to affect the system state. A replay attack does not require knowledge of system dynamics since once access to sensors is obtained, it continues replaying a previous measure. This permits the attacker to remain undetectable as long as the system state reported by sensors describes a good working condition. On the contrary, the attacker takes control of the system by modifying control inputs causing damage. A schematization of replay attack functioning is shown in **Figure 7**, notice that the only way to detect a replay attack is to add protection to the control signal entering actuators (Mo et al., 2014).

Figure 7. Scheme for replay attack strategy.

5.1.3. Covert attack

Covert attack (Li & Abdel-Khalik, 2021) follows a man in the middle strategy: the adversary is assumed to have resources to read and add to both control actuation command and sensors measurements, managing to have complete control on the system or a part of it. In practice, this is possible following two implementation strategies: (i) by augmenting physical actuators or modifying sensors; or (ii) by corrupting PLCs used by plant controller to implement different control and sensing operations. The second one described was the same implementation strategy used in a deeply analyzed in literature and reported cyber-attack called Stuxnet which managed to target Iranian control systems of gas pipelines and power plants (Falliere et al., 2011). The scheme in **Figure 8** exemplifies how the covert attack acts inside the system and how it is connected within the network. The two major components are: (i) a model that reproduces the real plant functioning and (ii) the covert controller. The actualization of such cyber-attack is strictly connected to an in-depth knowledge of the attacked system dynamics which permits to implement such components. For this reason, it is almost impossible to distinguish the operation of a covert attack from normal system operations.

Figure 8. Scheme for covert attack strategy.

5.1.4. Denial of service attack

Denial of service (DoS) attack has the purpose to interrupt communication between MTU and RTUs or PLCs or between RTUs and sensors or actuators. This type of attack manages to cut the link between system parts in order to disrupt the feedback control (Y. Yuan et al., 2013). The controllers are disconnected from the physical devices making impossible to monitor the process and leaving the system vulnerable to other possible attack actions. A practical way to implement such a scenario is by the utilization of disturbance devices such as jammers which can interrupt communication in a certain spatial area. **Figure 9** reports a schematization of such a scenario, communication can be interrupted from sensors to controllers, from controller to actuators, or simultaneously.

Figure 9. Scheme for denial of service attack strategy.

5.1.5. Eavesdropping attack

An eavesdropping attack consists in an appropriation of sensitive information as they are transmitted over the network between system components (Kao & Marculescu, 2006). The attack takes advantage of unsecured communication to access data moving inside the network. An eavesdropping attack can be difficult to detect since the information transmission will appear to operate in a normal condition. Even if it produces no tangible damage to the system, it could precede a more harmful scenario that needs an appropriate system knowledge to be conducted. For example, an eavesdropping attack can permit the adversary to steal information about plant operation states and make it possible to implement a dangerous covert attack. As shown in **Figure 10**, this type of attack only aims to hack communication to gain information.

Figure 10. Scheme for eavesdropping attack strategy.

5.1.6. Zero dynamics attack

This attack uses dynamic system vulnerabilities to be able to monitor and control the system behavior. More specifically, the attacker manages to make an unobservable state unstable. This vulnerability allows the attacker to disrupt the unobservable part of the system without being detected by controllers. A solution to avoid this kind of attacks is to update the architecture of the system in order to make all the states observable and using more sensors in order to avoid unobservable situations into the system (Chen et al., 2017). An attack of this type requires an optimal knowledge of attacked system dynamics and plant processes. The schematization of this attack strategy is not provided as it can be a combination of the ones shown in **Figure 6 – 10**.

5.1. Analysis of literature with respect to the classification

The data shown in **Table 1** are analyzed in this section. Firstly, various articles are distributed with respect to the industrial sector they focused on. To this extent, additional information is given by the column “Type of cyber-physical system” where the case study through which the authors test and validate their conclusions is reported. From the histogram in **Figure 11**, it is possible to notice how papers are distributed relative to industrial sectors. The manufacturing sector, with 15/39 (38%), represents the most documented area, with particular focus on fields such as additive manufacturing, composite materials, and assembly lines. In addition, the utilities sector, with 14/39 (36%), also constitutes another area on which much of the researchers' activity is focused: a lot of studies are available from both existing real-world structures and testbeds, i.e., small-scale models, or PC simulations models, too. Some of the utilities infrastructures are considered critical infrastructure, or parts of it, and they have already been the subject of multiple malicious attacks in the past, possibly justifying this increasing focus. In addition, there are also some papers focusing on the energy industry, specifically 5/39 (13%), chemical industries, with 3/39 (8%), and petrochemicals, with 2/39 (5%), which include nuclear plants, refineries, storage terminals or production with a natural tendency toward security and confidentiality.

Figure 11. Number of papers per industrial sector.

Figure 12. Number of papers per cyber-physical attack strategy. Please note that in some papers multiple attacks have been analyzed.

On the other hand, **Figure 12** details the type of cyber-physical attack strategy being considered in the research. Note that in a single paper more than one cyber-physical attack could be considered, and a total of 97 cyber-physical attacks have been detailed in the 39 papers. To this end, a major focus is given to stealth attacks (31/97, 32% ca.) stressing the fact that a single compromised measure could have a major impact on physical processes. Covert attacks are more complicated, as additional knowledge and resources are needed to successfully perform them. Nevertheless, a major emphasis is shown in literature to study them, too (27/97, 28% ca.). This result could be related to the fact that these attacks are usually highly disruptive and difficult to identify. The presence of eavesdropping and denial of service attacks is almost equal, i.e., 14/97 (14% ca.) and 13/97 (13% ca), respectively. They are simpler than the ones mentioned before, and usually their impact on system performance is lower. Finally, replay and zero dynamics attacks have been studied in 13/97 (8% ca.) and 12/97 (4% ca.) papers respectively. The lower number of studies concerning these strategies may be related to the fact that these strategies are highly articulated in their functioning.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The following report reviews scientific literature to highlight: (i) approaches for resilience and cyber resilience measurement, and (ii) strategies of cyber-physical attacks. The purpose of this report is to propose draft resilience metrics for possible cyber-physical attack scenarios in the testbed used in the RESIST project. The approach of comparing the baseline performance with the disrupted one is the one that will be adopted (see **Section 3**). The specificity of performance profiles will be defined once the experimental testbed will be completed, as they will be affected by the data collection process employed. However, at this stage it is important to point out at candidates metrics for the resilience assessment. Specifically, the Safety Control Structure (SCS, cf. D2000A) of the plant is reported in **Figure 13**.

With respect to the SCS, the feedback and control actions can be used to depict the current state of functioning of the plant. Nevertheless, feedback and control actions can be targeted by cyber-physical attacks, so they are not sufficient to depict the resilient performance. To collect such measures, there is the need to consider both information coming from plant functioning and operator's movements. Such measures should be paired with the measure of process parameters, specifically, water level in the tank and pressure in the pipelines (outputs in the SCS). Threshold values of the two measures could be defined to differentiate the criticality of the scenarios being simulated.

Comparing all these measures, a result similar to the one exemplified in **Figure 14** is expected. The plot in **Figure 14D** depicts a system performance over time. Specifically, the water level in the tank serves as an example. Such a level is measured by a sensor (cf. **Figure 14C**) which has been disrupted by a (e.g.,) a stealth attack strategy which managed to mask the measure, and faked the tank to be too full (i.e., red line in **Figure 14C** represents a compromised measure). As a result of the feedback measure, the actuator (i.e., the valve, cf. **Figure 14B**) closes, and the tank starts drawing water. This results in a difference with the expected baseline performance (i.e., dashed line in **Figure 14D**). However, the performance is recovered because of a controller (i.e., human operator) that intervenes on the valve. **Figure 14A** takes as an example the distance between the human operator and the valve. They get close to the valve and re-open it, refilling the tank. The cyber resilience of such simple scenario is evaluated by (e.g.) measuring the resilience triangle highlighted in **Figure 14D**.

Figure 14. Example of cyber resilience measure for the testbed plant.

Overall, this document serves as a baseline for drafting cyber resilience metrics for the case study of the RESIST project and guiding the definition of the cyber-physical attacks scenarios to be simulated. Developing additional details about both these aspects will be the focus of the subsequent project's activities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) – Mission 4 Education and Research – Component 2 From research to business - Investment 1.1, Prin 2022 Notice announced with DD No. 104 of 2/2/2022, entitled RESIST - RESilience management to Industrial Systems Threats, proposal code 2022YSAE2X

REFERENCES

- Arnaboldi, L., Czekster, R. M., Morisset, C., & Metere, R. (2020). Modelling Load-Changing Attacks in Cyber-Physical Systems. *Electronic Notes in Theoretical Computer Science*, 353, 39–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.entcs.2020.09.018>
- Attoh-Okine, N. O., Cooper, A. T., & Mensah, S. A. (2009). Formulation of resilience index of urban infrastructure using belief functions. *IEEE Systems Journal*, 3(2), 147–153. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2009.2019148>
- Aven, T. (2019). The Call for a Shift from Risk to Resilience: What Does it Mean? *Risk Analysis*, 39(6), 1196–1203. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.13247>
- Banik, S., Banik, T., Hossain, S. M. M., & Saha, S. K. (2023). *Implementing Man-in-the-Middle Attack to Investigate Network Vulnerabilities in Smart Grid Test-bed* (arXiv:2306.00234). arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2306.00234>
- Bruneau, M., & Reinhorn, A. (2007). Exploring the concept of seismic resilience for acute care facilities. *Earthquake Spectra*, 23(1), 41–62. <https://doi.org/10.1193/1.2431396>
- Burbano, L., Combita, L. F., Quijano, N., & Rueda, S. (2021). Dynamic Data Integration for Resilience to Sensor Attacks in Multi-Agent Systems. *IEEE Access*, 9, 31236–31245. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3059560>
- Cárdenas, A. A., Amin, S., Lin, Z.-S., Huang, Y.-L., Huang, C.-Y., & Sastry, S. (n.d.). *Attacks against process control systems: Risk assessment, detection, and response*.
- Carreño, I. L., Scaglione, A., Zlotnik, A., Deka, D., & Sundar, K. (2020). An adversarial model for attack vector vulnerability analysis on power and gas delivery operations. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 189, 106777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2020.106777>
- Chekole, E. G., Ochoa, M., & Chattopadhyay, S. (2021). *SCOPE: Secure Compiling of PLCs in Cyber-Physical Systems* (arXiv:2012.12529). arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2012.12529>
- Chen, Y., Kar, S., & Moura, J. M. F. (2017). *Dynamic Attack Detection in Cyber-Physical Systems with Side Initial State Information*.
- Coppolino, L., D’Antonio, S., Giuliano, V., Mazzeo, G., & Romano, L. (2022). A framework for Seveso-compliant cyber-physical security testing in sensitive industrial plants. *Computers in Industry*, 136, 103589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2021.103589>
- Dai, J., Chen, W., & Zhou, X. (2024). Fuzzy high order differentiator observer based resilient control for distributed battery energy storage systems against unbounded FDI attacks. *IET Control Theory & Applications*, cth2.12622. <https://doi.org/10.1049/cth2.12622>
- Dan, G., & Sandberg, H. (2010). Stealth Attacks and Protection Schemes for State Estimators in Power Systems. *2010 First IEEE International Conference on Smart Grid Communications*, 214–219. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SMARTGRID.2010.5622046>
- Dedousis, P., Stergiopoulos, G., Arampatzis, G., & Gritzalis, D. (2021). A Security-Aware Framework for Designing Industrial Engineering Processes. *IEEE Access*, 9, 163065–163085. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3134759>
- Dehlaghi-Ghadim, A., Balador, A., Moghadam, M. H., Hansson, H., & Conti, M. (2023). ICSSIM — A framework for building industrial control systems security testbeds. *Computers in Industry*, 148, 103906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2023.103906>

- Dhs. (2014). *The 2014 Quadrennial Homeland Security Review*.
- Dong, X., Wang, Z., & Guo, S. (2022). State Estimation and Attack Reconstruction of Picking Robot for a Cyber-Physical System. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2022, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/6240165>
- Elnour, M., Noorizadeh, M., Shakerpour, M., Meskin, N., Khan, K., & Jain, R. (2023). A Machine Learning Based Framework for Real-Time Detection and Mitigation of Sensor False Data Injection Cyber-Physical Attacks in Industrial Control Systems. *IEEE Access*, 11, 86977–86998. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3303015>
- Falliere, N., Murchu, O. L., & Chien, E. (2011). *W32. Stuxnet dossier*.
- Graves, L., King, W. E., Carrion, P., Shao, S., Shamsaei, N., & Yampolskiy, M. (2021). Sabotaging metal additive manufacturing: Powder delivery system manipulation and material-dependent effects. *Additive Manufacturing*, 46, 102029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2021.102029>
- Haque, M. A., De Teyou, G. K., Shetty, S., & Krishnappa, B. (2018). Cyber Resilience Framework for Industrial Control Systems: Concepts, Metrics, and Insights. *2018 IEEE International Conference on Intelligence and Security Informatics (ISI)*, 25–30. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISI.2018.8587398>
- Haque, M. A., Shetty, S., & Krishnappa, B. (2019). Cyber-physical system resilience: Frameworks, metrics, complexities, challenges, and future directions. *Complexity Challenges in Cyber Physical Systems: Using Modeling and Simulation (M&S) to Support Intelligence, Adaptation and Autonomy*, 301–337. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119552482.ch12>
- Hindy, H., Brosset, D., Bayne, E., Seem, A., & Bellekens, X. (2019). Improving SIEM for Critical SCADA Water Infrastructures Using Machine Learning. In S. K. Katsikas, F. Cuppens, N. Cuppens, C. Lambrinoudakis, A. Antón, S. Gritzalis, J. Mylopoulos, & C. Kalloniatis (Eds.), *Computer Security* (Vol. 11387, pp. 3–19). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-12786-2_1
- Holling, C. S. (2013). Resilience and stability of ecological systems. *The Future of Nature: Documents of Global Change*, 245–256. <https://doi.org/10.12987/9780300188479-023>
- Hollnagel, E., Woods, D. D., & Leveson, N. (2012). Resilience engineering: Concepts and precepts. In *Resilience Engineering: Concepts and Precepts*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/qshc.2006.018390>
- Hosseini, S., Barker, K., & Ramirez-Marquez, J. E. (2016). A review of definitions and measures of system resilience. *Reliability Engineering and System Safety*, 145, 47–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2015.08.006>
- Huang, K., Zhou, C., Tian, Y.-C., Yang, S., & Qin, Y. (2018). Assessing the Physical Impact of Cyberattacks on Industrial Cyber-Physical Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 65(10), 8153–8162. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2018.2798605>
- Humayed, A., Lin, J., Li, F., & Luo, B. (2017). Cyber-Physical Systems Security—A Survey. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 4(6), 1802–1831. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2017.2703172>
- Iaiani, M., Tugnoli, A., & Cozzani, V. (2023). Identification of cyber-risks for the control and safety instrumented systems: A synergic framework for the process industry. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 172, 69–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2023.01.078>
- Ibrahim, M., Al-Hindawi, Q., Elhafiz, R., Alsheikh, A., & Alquq, O. (2019). Attack Graph Implementation and Visualization for Cyber Physical Systems. *Processes*, 8(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr8010012>
- Kang, B., Maynard, P., McLaughlin, K., Sezer, S., Andren, F., Seitzl, C., Kupzog, F., & Strasser, T. (2015). Investigating cyber-physical attacks against IEC 61850 photovoltaic inverter installations. *2015 IEEE 20th Conference on Emerging Technologies & Factory Automation (ETFA)*, 1–8.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ETFA.2015.7301457>

Kao, J. C., & Marculescu, R. (2006). *Eavesdropping minimization via transmission power control in ad-hoc wireless networks*.

Katulić, F., Sumina, D., Groš, S., & Erceg, I. (2023). Protecting Modbus/TCP-Based Industrial Automation and Control Systems Using Message Authentication Codes. *IEEE Access*, *11*, 47007–47023. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3275443>

Khalid, A., Khan, Z. H., Idrees, M., Kirisci, P., Ghrairi, Z., Thoben, K.-D., & Pannek, J. (2022). Understanding vulnerabilities in cyber physical production systems. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, *35*(6), 569–582. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0951192X.2021.1992656>

Li, Y., & Abdel-Khalik, H. S. (2021). Data trustworthiness signatures for nuclear reactor dynamics simulation. *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, *133*, 103612. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2020.103612>

Liu, Y., Ning, P., & Reiter, M. K. (2011). False data injection attacks against state estimation in electric power grids. *ACM Transactions on Information and System Security*, *14*(1), 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1952982.1952995>

Loukas, G., Yoon, Y., Sakellari, G., Vuong, T., & Heartfield, R. (2017). Computation offloading of a vehicle's continuous intrusion detection workload for energy efficiency and performance. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, *73*, 83–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2016.08.005>

Maggi, F., Balduzzi, M., Vosseler, R., Rösler, M., Quadrini, W., Tavola, G., Pogliani, M., Quarta, D., & Zanero, S. (2021). Smart Factory Security: A Case Study on a Modular Smart Manufacturing System. *Procedia Computer Science*, *180*, 666–675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.01.289>

Mahvash, H., Taher, S. A., & Guerrero, J. M. (2024). A New Nonlinear Virtual Inertia Approach to Mitigate Destructive Effects of Cyber Attacks on Active Power and Rotor Speed Profiles of Wind Turbine DFIG Sustainable Energy Production. *Smart Grids and Sustainable Energy*, *9*(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40866-024-00201-9>

Mangrolia, B., Cleeman, J., Patel, A., Wei, S., Shao, C., Xu, H., & Malhotra, R. (2024). Continuing minimal-defect production under material integrity cyberattacks. *Manufacturing Letters*, *40*, 54–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mfglet.2024.02.006>

Martin, R. (2012). Regional economic resilience, hysteresis and recessionary shocks. *Journal of Economic Geography*, *12*(1), 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeg/lbr019>

Mo, Y., Chabukswar, R., & Sinopoli, B. (2014). Detecting Integrity Attacks on SCADA Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, *22*(4), 1396–1407. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCST.2013.2280899>

National Institute of Standards and Technology. (2018). *Framework for improving critical infrastructure cybersecurity* (Vol. 535).

Nedeljković, D., Jakovljević, Ž., & Miljković, Z. (2020). The detection of sensor signal attacks in industrial control systems. *FME Transactions*, *48*(2), 7–12. <https://doi.org/10.5937/fmet2001007N>

Nedeljković, D., Jakovljević, Ž., Miljković, Z., & Pajić, M. (2020). Detection of cyber-attacks in systems with distributed control based on support vector regression. *Telfor Journal*, *12*(2), 104–109. <https://doi.org/10.5937/telfor2002104N>

Olijnyk, J., Bond, B., & Rrushi, J. (2022). Design and Emulation of Physics-Centric Cyberattacks on an Electrical Power Transformer. *IEEE Access*, *10*, 15227–15246. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3148046>

- Palleti, V. R., Adepur, S., Mishra, V. K., & Mathur, A. (2021). Cascading effects of cyber-attacks on interconnected critical infrastructure. *Cybersecurity*, 4(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42400-021-00071-z>
- Palleti, V. R., Mishra, V. K., Ahmed, C. M., & Mathur, A. (2021). Can Replay Attacks Designed to Steal Water from Water Distribution Systems Remain Undetected? *ACM Transactions on Cyber-Physical Systems*, 5(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3406764>
- Pearce, H., Yanamandra, K., Gupta, N., & Karri, R. (2021). *FLAW3D: A Trojan-based Cyber Attack on the Physical Outcomes of Additive Manufacturing* (arXiv:2104.09562). arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2104.09562>
- Rajkumar, R., Lee, I., Sha, L., & Stankovic, J. (2010). Cyber-physical systems: The next computing revolution. *Proceedings - Design Automation Conference*, 731–736. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1837274.1837461>
- Ranabhat, B., Clements, J., Gatlin, J., Hsiao, K.-T., & Yampolskiy, M. (2018). *Optimal Sabotage Attack on Composite Material Parts* (arXiv:1810.03010). arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.03010>
- Rashid, N., Wan, J., Quirós, G., Canedo, A., & Faruque, M. A. Al. (2017). Modeling and simulation of cyberattacks for resilient cyber-physical systems. *IEEE International Conference on Automation Science and Engineering, 2017-August*, 988–993. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COASE.2017.8256231>
- Robles-Durazno, A., Moradpoor, N., McWhinnie, J., Russell, G., & Porcel-Bustamante, J. (2021). Implementation and Evaluation of Physical, Hybrid, and Virtual Testbeds for Cybersecurity Analysis of Industrial Control Systems. *Symmetry*, 13(3), 519. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym13030519>
- Rose, A. (2009). Economic Resilience To Disasters. *Community and Regional Resilience Institute*, 1(4).
- Sachdeva, N., Obheroi, R. K., Srivastava, A., & Nehal, S. K. (2018). Diffusion of industry 4.0 in manufacturing sector-An innovative framework. *2017 International Conference on Infocom Technologies and Unmanned Systems: Trends and Future Directions, ICTUS 2017, 2018-Janua*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTUS.2017.8286025>
- Sheffi, Y. (2006). The resilient enterprise: Overcoming vulnerability for competitive advantage. *Choice Reviews Online*, 43(06), 43-3481-43-3481. <https://doi.org/10.5860/choice.43-3481>
- Stetter, R., Witczak, M., & Till, M. (2022). Cyber-Security Aware Design of Automated Systems. *Proceedings of the Design Society*, 2, 1985–1994. <https://doi.org/10.1017/pds.2022.201>
- Takiddin, A., Rath, S., Ismail, M., & Sahoo, S. (2022). Data-Driven Detection of Stealth Cyber-Attacks in DC Microgrids. *IEEE Systems Journal*, 16(4), 6097–6106. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2022.3183140>
- Teixeira, A., Pérez, D., Sandberg, H., & Johansson, K. H. (2012). Attack models and scenarios for networked control systems. *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on High Confidence Networked Systems*, 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2185505.2185515>
- Tierney, K., & Bruneau, M. (2007). Conceptualizing and measuring resilience: A key to disaster loss reduction. *TR News*, 250, 14–17.
- Umsonst, D., & Sandberg, H. (2022). Experimental evaluation of sensor attacks and defense mechanisms in feedback systems. *Control Engineering Practice*, 124, 105178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conengprac.2022.105178>
- Van Bossuyt, D. L., & O'Halloran, B. M. (2019). A Method to Choose Between Automation and Human Operators for Recovery Actions During a Cyber Attack. *Procedia Computer Science*, 153, 352–360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.05.089>
- Wei, D., & Ji, K. (2010). Resilient industrial control system (RICS): Concepts, formulation, metrics, and

insights. *Proceedings - ISRCS 2010 - 3rd International Symposium on Resilient Control Systems*, 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISRCS.2010.5603480>

Wu, M., Song, J., Lucas Lin, L. W., Aurelle, N., Liu, Y., Ding, B., Song, Z., & Moon, Y. B. (2018). Establishment of intrusion detection testbed for CyberManufacturing systems. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 26, 1053–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2018.07.142>

Yaacoub, J.-P. A., Salman, O., Noura, H. N., Kaaniche, N., Chehab, A., & Malli, M. (2020). Cyber-physical systems security: Limitations, issues and future trends. *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, 77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpro.2020.103201>

Yampolskiy, M., Schutzle, L., Vaidya, U., & Yasinsac, A. (2015). Security Challenges of Additive Manufacturing with Metals and Alloys. In M. Rice & S. Sheno (Eds.), *Critical Infrastructure Protection IX* (Vol. 466, pp. 169–183). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-26567-4_11

Yuan, S., Yang, M., & Reniers, G. (2024). Integrated process safety and process security risk assessment of industrial cyber-physical systems in chemical plants. *Computers in Industry*, 155, 104056. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2023.104056>

Yuan, Y., Zhu, Q., Sun, F., Wang, Q., & Basar, T. (2013). *Resilient control of cyber-physical systems against Denial-of-Service attacks*.

Zhang, M., Chen, C.-Y., Kao, B.-C., Qamsane, Y., Shao, Y., Lin, Y., Shi, E., Mohan, S., Barton, K., Moyne, J., & Mao, Z. M. (2019). Towards Automated Safety Vetting of PLC Code in Real-World Plants. *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, 522–538. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2019.00034>